

A simulation of the photoconversion efficiency of P3HT:PCBM bulk heterojunction: An insight on the charge collection efficiency

Francesco Scotognella

Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129 Torino, Italy

E-mail: francesco.scotognella@polito.it

Abstract

In organic bulk heterojunction solar cells, the internal quantum efficiency can be considered as the product of the absorption efficiency, the exciton diffusion efficiency, the charge transfer efficiency, and the charge collection efficiency. In previous studies, it has been reported that charge transfer and charge collection is very high in these solar cells, approaching 100 %. With a Monte Carlo simulation approach that considers the hopping of charges within the two materials of the heterojunctions, it is highlighted that an estimate of the charge collection efficiency can be evaluated considering that a certain number of charges do not reach the electrodes because of the random arrangement of the two materials in the heterojunction. The case of P3HT:PCBM (1:1 ratio) has been analyzed in this study.

Organic solar cells, in which the active photovoltaic materials include conjugated molecules and polymers, have been widely studied in the last years [1]. Considering the low charge mobility of molecules and polymers, the concept of bulk heterojunction has been a technological breakthrough in the field [2]. To simulate the optoelectronic properties of organic bulk heterojunction solar cells, many admirable models have been reported in the literature [3,4]. It turns out that the studies of Peumans et al. [5] and Forrest [5] are very interesting from the points of view of clarity and depth. Following these works, the internal quantum efficiency for an organic solar cell can be written as

$$\eta_{IQE} = \eta_A \eta_{ED} \eta_{CT} \eta_{CC} \quad [1]$$

Where η_A is the absorption efficiency, η_{ED} is the exciton diffusion efficiency, η_{CT} is the charge transfer efficiency, and η_{CC} is the charge collection efficiency. η_{CT} , the charge transfer efficiency, can be considered very high in organic bulk heterojunction solar cells approaching 100% [5–7].

The absorption efficiency [6]

$$\eta_A = 1 - e^{-\alpha d} \quad [2]$$

And exciton diffusion efficiency [6]

$$\eta_{ED} = e^{-d/L_D} \quad [3]$$

In Equations 2 and 3, d is the thickness (100 nm in this study) and L_D is the exciton diffusion length (5 nm as in Ref. [8]). $1/\alpha$ is 200 nm as in Ref. [6].

Concerning the charge collection efficiency η_{CC} , Forrest reports that the values of such efficiency approaches 100% for organic photovoltaic systems, mainly because of the built-in electric field [5,6]. An estimate of the charge collection efficiency η_{CC} can be performed with a Monte Carlo simulation that studies the percolation of electrons and holes in a three-dimensional matrix. In this work, the case of a P3HT:PCBM (1:1 ratio) bulk heterojunction has been considered. Such three-dimensional matrix is a simplified representation of the bulk heterojunction in which each element depicts a domain of about 5 nm of diameter of the same material, and the matrix is built with a random arrangement of the two materials of the heterojunction, in the attempt to describe the architecture of the bulk heterojunction. In the simulation, the exciton dissociation occurs at the interface between P3HT and PCBM. The charges hop only in the proper material in the junction (i.e., holes in P3HT and electrons in PCBM). In the simulation the holes need to reach the bottom electrode and electrons need to reach the top electrode. In Figure 1 a histogram of the numbers of hops for holes

in P3HT to reach the bottom electrode and for electrons in PCBM to reach to top electrode. When the number of hops reach 10000, a value that well above the typical values of the distributions, the hopping simulation stops and for that case it is decreed that the charges failed to reach the electrodes, consequently lowering the charge collection efficiency η_{CC} .

Figure 1. Histogram of the number of hops of charges in the two materials, i.e., P3HT and PCBM, of the bulk heterojunction to reach the electrodes (1000 simulations).

In a study where of simulates for 1000 times the dissociation of an exciton at the interface between P3HT and PCBM and the charges percolate to the electrodes, 943 pairs of electrons and lacunae manage to reach the electrodes, Therefore, the charge collection efficiency $\eta_{CC} = 0.943$ has been found the P3HT:PCBM heterojunction. According to this study, for the P3HT:PCBM bulk heterojunction η_{IQE} is 16.05 %, with an absorption efficiency η_A of 39.35 %, an exciton diffusion efficiency η_{ED} of 43.25 %, and the aforementioned charge collection efficiency η_{CC} of 94.30 %.

The external quantum efficiency can be written as

$$\eta_{EQE} = (1 - R)\eta_{IQE} \quad [4]$$

Where R is the reflectivity of the substrate-air interface (in the spectral region between 300 and 1100 nm). To calculate R the transfer matrix method has been employed [9] and the complex refractive index of BK7 optical glass has been taken from [10]. Thus, for a P3HT:PCBM (1:1) bulk heterojunction the η_{EQE} 15.38 %.

Considering that the highest certified efficiency of a P3HT:PCBM solar cell is 5.4 %, other factors could be considered in the simulation. In the charge collection, the inter-site hopping rates can be taken into account [11,12]. A deeper discussion can be also pursued on the charge transfer efficiency [7].

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